

ATTENTION MAPS FOR ATMOREP: STUDYING LARGE-SCALE REPRESENTATION LEARNING OF ATMOSPHERIC DYNAMICS

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ABSTRACT

With the escalating threat of climate change, innovative technological solutions have become imperative. In this light, we introduce "AtmoRep," a cutting-edge, large-scale transformer designed specifically for the representation learning of atmospheric dynamics. While transformers have revolutionized numerous domains, their introduction to the field of weather modeling is relatively nascent. Beyond merely achieving enhanced precision, our transformer model demonstrates robustness, especially in zero-shot tasks. However, with the power of these models comes the pressing need for interpretability. This paper delves into the generation, organization, and interpretation of attention maps, a cornerstone of transformer architectures. We tackle the technical challenges associated with extracting these attention maps and the more abstract difficulty of their organization. In doing so, we hope to foster a more transparent and scientifically rigorous methodology in large-scale weather modeling.

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1 INTRODUCTION

With the rise of rapid climate change and the subsequent surge in extreme weather events, the need for precise and dependable weather models has never been more crucial to safeguarding human lives, autonomy, property, and social infrastructure [1]. The dominant weather models used today are based on numerical methods, a set of algorithms in which computers approximate solutions to a large number of complex equations that generally cannot be resolved analytically [2]. While these models have made tremendous strides in recent decades, numerical models still suffer from very high computational cost, difficulty describing physical processes, and an inability to do long-term forecasting [3]. With the best 10-14 day forecasts achieving only 50% accuracy (Fig. 1), and longer-term predictions falling to near 0% accuracy after just a few more weeks, it's clear that modeling the weather, even with modern computing, is an extraordinary challenge [4].

Figure 1: Data from ECMWF [5].

The primary difficulty in weather modeling comes from the fact that it is a complex nonlinear dynamic system. In other words, it's chaotic. Edward Lorenz, a 20th-century mathematician and meteorologist who helped found the study of chaos, brought to mind the popular example of the "butterfly effect" when describing the difficulties in weather forecasting. The "butterfly effect" is a metaphorical example in which details of a tornado are influenced by perturbations as minor as a distant butterfly flapping its wings several weeks earlier. Although this example itself is somewhat exaggerated, it is widely accepted that even small changes to how one sets the initial conditions of the atmosphere before prediction can lead to drastic consequences later on.

Provided this internal constraint, finding ways to enhance our models for longer-term and more detailed predictions is challenging. However, with the rise of deep learning methods, there is good reason to suspect we can develop models that complement classical numerical modeling, even moving beyond its capabilities in some respects. Research has already shown promise in the application of RNNs, GNNs, and FNOs for the forecasting of complex spatiotemporal dynamics [6, 7, 8]. Thus, given the nature of this problem and the recent success of deep learning, we introduce AtmoRep [9]: a stochastic, generative deep neural network designed for advanced representation learning. Built on a transformer encoder-decoder architecture [10], this 3.5 billion parameter model represents a pivotal step on our path toward effective and accurate weather modeling. Since AtmoRep takes advantage of attention mechanisms, it is uniquely poised to handle the complex inter-scale and inter-field dependencies fundamental to weather modeling. Furthermore, AtmoRep is a foundational model, meaning that it is pre-trained on a vast amount of data and has the ability to be fine-tuned for more specific tasks such as bias correction and downscaling. Even without fine-tuning, AtmoRep shows impressive zero-shot capabilities on non-forecasting tasks including temporal interpolation, model correction, and counterfactuals. Think- the robustness of OpenAIs GPT [11], applied for the first time to Earth science.

AtmoRep is a joint collaboration between CERN scientists, University of Magdeburg computer scientists,

and professionals from the Jülich Supercomputing Center. AtmoRep aims for a complete picture of atmospheric dynamics through the application of large-scale representation learning [12]. AtmoRep seeks to eventually be realized within the framework of the *EMP²* project [13] which will deploy AtmoRep on the interTwin engine, a general-purpose scientific digital-twin engine providing robust software components to the project [14]. This will allow the model to be deployed for a variety of downstream tasks in a versatile format.

During my internship at CERN, I contributed to AtmoRep in the following ways:

- Developed an attention map generation pipeline in the codebase.
- Developed WebUI for easy model visualization: <https://www.atmorep.org/attention/attention.html>.
- Started the integration of AtmoRep within the digital twin prototype developed by the interTwin team at CERN.

2 MODEL DETAILS

A. ATTENTION MECHANISM

The most elementary component in the architecture of the AtmoRep model is the attention mechanism. Though attention existed in some capacity beforehand, in 2017 Vaswani et al. revolutionized machine learning with their paper, "Attention Is All You Need" [10]. Attention is traditionally defined for three matrices called queries Q keys K and values V as follows:

$$\text{Attention}(Q, K, V) = \text{softmax} \left(\frac{QK^T}{\sqrt{dk}} \right) V$$

where dk is the dimensionality of K , the division of which supports gradient stability in the network.

Q , K , and V are distinct high-dimensional vector representations of the input sequence, each generated by passing the input through separate linear layers. The intuition for these roles can be likened to elements within a database table. In this context:

- **Queries (Q):** These represent the *search queries* one might use to fetch specific records from a database. They define what we are currently looking for or interested in.
- **Keys (K):** Analogous to the *index columns* in a database table. Just as the index columns help us rapidly locate the relevant rows in a table, the keys in the attention mechanism help the model determine the relevance or match with the given query.
- **Values (V):** These are akin to the *content rows* in a database that store the actual information. Once the right index (or key) is located using the search query, the corresponding value is retrieved, representing the actual content or data we're interested in.

In this conceptual model, the attention scores, akin to the relevance scores in a database search, prioritize which records (or values) are most pertinent to the given query. This provides a flexible mechanism for the model to selectively focus on different parts of the input. Much like how a database returns the most relevant records based on the search query, or how humans pay selective attention to different parts of information based on their relevance or significance. In this architecture, the attention scores, generated by the dot product between Q and K , give a measure of relevance between different parts of the input. By using the *softmax* function, we ensure that these scores are normalized and sum up to one, making the mechanism probabilistic.

As seen in the left panel of Fig. 2 we also have the option of applying a mask to the attention scores. This sets some values in the matrix to zero in order to perform predictions later on. The right panel shows multi-head attention, a process in which Q , K , and V are split up along their embedding dimension. Attention is then computed h times where h denotes the number of heads. This multi-headed architecture enables the model to

Figure 2: Attention Mechanism [10].

capture various aspects of the information, diversifying the attention focus and enhancing the richness of the model’s representations. This concurrent processing across different heads allows for better capture of diverse relationships and patterns within the data, leading to improved performance in many tasks.

B. TRANSFORMER

The transformer’s architecture is based on an encoder-decoder structure as depicted in Fig. 3 where the left side of the image is the encoder and the right side is the decoder. The encoder segment ingests the input sequence, token by token, and produces a continuous representation that captures the essence and context of the input. Each encoder layer consists of self-attention mechanisms, enabling each token to focus on different parts of the input based on relevance. In contrast, the decoder receives this continuous representation and, layer by layer, generates the output sequence. With its own set of self-attention layers, the decoder not only maintains the context from the encoder but also pays attention to its own previously generated tokens, ensuring coherent and contextually relevant output. This encoder-decoder pairing is what empowers transformers to excel at representation learning, as hierarchical feature extraction is often built into the consecutive encoder decoder blocks.

Figure 3: The Transformer - model architecture. [10].

Introduced in the same paper by Vaswani et al., the transformer integrated the attention mechanism to construct a cohesive model that, while initially applied to NLP tasks, has shown promise in many areas of ML. Instead of relying on the sequential processing inherent to recurrent models, transformers utilized parallelized attention mechanisms, allowing them to consider all tokens in an input sequence simultaneously. This not only conferred a computational edge but also endowed the architecture with a deeper contextual understanding. With the integration of feed-forward networks, layer normalization, and skip connections, transformers swiftly evolved into the preferred architecture for an array of tasks, launching the world into the generative era.

C. DATASET

The development of AtmoRep has become possible thanks to two main achievements- transformer architectures and the availability of large-scale continuous climate datasets. AtmoRep is trained on predicting masked or distorted tokens using the ERA5 reanalysis dataset. ERA5 is a product of the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF), providing hourly atmospheric and surface parameters from 1940 to the present; "reanalysis" refers to the use of modern forecasting models, data assimilation systems, and machine learning techniques, to synthesize historical weather data into a consistent, global dataset [15]. To date ERA5 represents the most complete, consistent, and accurate record of atmospheric observations, making it the ideal choice for this project. ERA5 data on all years between 1979 and 2017 is fed into the model for training, which then allows for robust task-agnostic (with and without fine-tuning) applications as laid out in Fig. 4.

Figure 4: The AtmoRep pipeline.

D. MULTIFORMER

Transformers have already shown extraordinary promise in realms such as NLP where one class of training data is being handled by the model. However, describing weather phenomena requires a rich understanding of not just individual variables, but also their inherent interdependencies and dynamics across multiple scales of time and space. Parameters such as temperature, humidity, wind speed and direction, pressure, and solar radiation are not isolated elements, but instead form an intricate network of interdependencies. For instance, humidity levels are closely tied to both temperature and air pressure, affecting phenomena such as cloud formation and precipitation. Divergence and curl in wind patterns, often dictated by pressure gradients, play a crucial role in the movement of air masses, thereby influencing cloud development and, consequently, precipitation events. Furthermore, variables like orographic effects and sea-land temperature contrasts contribute to localized weather systems. Therefore, weather emerges as a result of a complex interplay between multiple factors, each of which is governed by physical laws but manifests in an integrated manner to produce the observed meteorological conditions.

To tackle this unique challenge inherent in generative weather modeling, we introduce the multiformer—a variant of the standard transformer architecture. The novelty lies in the use of cross-attention to intimately

couple diverse physical fields, addressing their inherent interplay in shaping weather patterns. Each of these fields, such as vorticity, divergence, vertical velocity, temperature, specific humidity, and total precipitation, possesses its unique characteristics and dynamic ranges. If we were to process these fields collectively in a single transformer, the attention mechanism would scale quadratically with the combined data size, leading to computational inefficiencies. Moreover, the nuances of each field could get overshadowed by dominant patterns in others. By leveraging a dedicated transformer for each field—connected through cross-attention as seen in the red lines of Fig. 5—we ensure that fields can communicate effectively while retaining their distinct features. This architecture not only preserves the uniqueness of each field but also captures their intricate interactions, paving the way for a more accurate representation of weather phenomena.

Figure 5: AtmoRep Architecture.

The multiformer architecture, as depicted in Fig. 5, consists of sequential encoder blocks (at the top) paired with a corresponding set of decoder blocks (at the bottom) in a U-Net-like fashion [16]. Specifically, connections are established such that the first encoder is linked to the last decoder, the second encoder to the second-last decoder, and so forth. This design enables the model to extract features at various levels of granularity, thereby optimizing representation learning. At the end of the multiformer architecture, AtmoRep employs an ensemble of per-field tail networks, which transform the internal latent representations into a grid-based spatial-temporal depiction of physical fields. Unlike traditional numerical weather prediction ensembles, which introduce variability via perturbations to initial conditions, AtmoRep’s ensemble derives its variability directly from the inherent fluctuations in the ERA5 training data, offering a distinctive and efficient approach to represent atmospheric state distributions. We also note that positional encoding is done via harmonic functions and embedding is achieved through a linear layer.

E. TRAINING

Atmorep was trained at the Jülich Supercomputing Centre on the JUWELS booster which has clusters of 4 NVIDIA Ampere GPUs [17]. Despite this computing power, it is still too demanding to train with the entire ERA5 dataset on each epoch. To address this issue, we adopted a Monte Carlo-based approach to training. In each training cycle, we randomly select a subset of the complete dataset to process. This method involves first choosing a limited number of year-month combinations and then randomly selecting spatial regions to focus on. Since each task can proceed independently of the others, this operation is easily parallelizable across multiple GPUs.

The training process takes place in two steps. We first train each individual field separately and then train them in the coupled model depicted in Fig. 5. This allows us to mitigate the quadratic training cost of attention while still forcing the model to be context-aware across multiple fields. The model is trained on the BERT-like task [18] of predicting masked or distorted tokens with a high masking ratio (around .75). Tokens are predicted within the local attention neighborhood of a spacetime hypercube (Fig. 6) with dimensions 36h x 1500 km x

3000 km. The model is thus spatially local which allows it to learn how the atmosphere behaves regionally, it is also much more memory efficient.

Figure 6: The large spacetime hypercube is divided into smaller tokens.

After training, AtmoRep shows impressive zero-shot capabilities on tasks including temporal interpolation, model correction, and counterfactuals. Temporal interpolation describes a task in which the model generates output with higher temporal resolution than the input. Model correction refers to a process in which the model is able to process data taken from related but different distributions than those seen during pre-training. Finally, are "what if" scenarios used to assess the impact of specific variables, such as human-induced changes, on the occurrence and intensity of events like extreme weather, often by comparing actual events with simulated ones under different conditions. After fine-tuning the model with methods such as bias correction, which involves using other observational data to fine-tune the model, we are able to push the model's capabilities further for task-specific applications. Fine-tuning also allows the model to achieve better downscaling performance, where the resolution of ERA5 data is mapped to higher resolution, and improved forecasting skills overall. For more details on the results please see the pre-print [9].

3 ATTENTION MAPS

A. THEORY

An attention map is the matrix derived from multiplying queries Q by keys K within an attention block as described in section 2B. Both Q and K are context-aware vector representations of the input tokens that hold progressively more information as they move through subsequent attention blocks in the network (Fig. 5). Namely, we multiply $Q_h \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times E_h}$ by $K_h \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times E_h}$, where E_h is the embedding dimension after being segmented to each head and N is the number of tokens. By performing QK^T , we compute the dot product between each token vector representation and every other in the sequence, thus generating an attention matrix $A_h \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times N}$. This effectively measures the dot product similarity between tokens, or how relevant parts of the input are to others in nearby space and time. This similarity is known as the attention score, and the matrix of all attention scores is called the attention map. A higher attention score suggests that the model perceives those tokens as being relevant to each other and to the overall network in general, whereas a low attention score suggests certain relationships don't influence the future state of the system.

In the architecture of any transformer-like model, the computation of attention matrices occurs at various stages, for instance, the encoder, decoder, or any given attention block. A crucial academic question revolves around the optimal stage from which to extract these attention maps for interpretability or further analysis. One prevailing approach is to draw attention maps from the final layer, as it is closest to the output and typically encapsulates a higher degree of contextual information. However, each layer within the architecture captures unique facets of the data, with earlier layers generally focusing on rudimentary features and intermediate layers capturing more complex relationships. An alternative strategy involves accumulating attention across multiple

layers. This method combines the attention scores from successive stages to provide a more nuanced understanding of how different segments of the input relate to each other or contribute to the final output. The choice of stage for attention extraction is not trivial and can be contingent upon the particular analytical objectives one aims to achieve. In this paper, we generate maps using both approaches for a more comprehensive analysis of the model's behavior.

Once the attention matrix is obtained from the model, in order to create a visual representation of how the model focuses on the input, the dimensionality of our attention matrix must go from $A_h \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times N}$ to $A_h \in \mathbb{R}^N$. This is because the attention mechanism operates by comparing each token to every other token in the sequence (yielding the attention matrix $A_h \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times N}$). Say $A_{h_{ij}}$ represents the attention score between the i^{th} and j^{th} tokens, $A_{h_{ij}}$ would signify the attention score between the i^{th} and j^{th} tokens, building up a matrix that captures all information for each token with every other in its attention neighborhood. This matrix captures the full complexity of inter-token relationships but poses a challenge for direct interpretation. To remap these attention scores back onto the original input—whether it be an image or a text sequence—it becomes necessary to employ a dimensionality reduction strategy, converting A_h into $A_h \in \mathbb{R}^N$. This facilitates a one-to-one mapping with the original input, as it shares the same number of tokens and dimensions. Two simplistic but effective strategies are: 1) *Averaging Across Keys*, mathematically defined as $A_{h_{avg}} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{j=1}^N A_{h_{ij}}$. This approach offers the benefit of summarizing the overall 'relevance' of each token with respect to all others, but may dilute strong attention relationships. 2) *Focusing on a Specific Token*, encapsulated by $A_{h_i} = [A_{h_{i1}}, A_{h_{i2}}, \dots, A_{h_{iN}}]$. This method is particularly useful when the attention relationship with a specific token (e.g., the subject of a sentence or a focal point in an image) is of interest. While other methods like Max Pooling and Principal Component Analysis provide additional options, we opt to focus on these first two strategies for their straightforward interpretability and computational efficiency.

Attention maps have emerged as a pivotal tool in the field of machine learning, particularly within the realm of deep learning for NLP and computer vision. These graphical representations offer insights into what the neural network is focusing on while performing its task. By visualizing attention maps, researchers can gain an understanding of the model's internal state, thereby providing a window into the often elusive interpretability of these complex systems [19]. Furthermore, attention maps have practical implications; for instance, they can help identify regions of an input (e.g., words in a sentence or areas in an image) that are most salient for a given output, which can be invaluable for debugging or improving model performance. In medical imaging, attention maps have facilitated the localization of anomalies in images without explicit annotations, essentially acting as a form of weakly supervised learning [20]. Thus, attention maps serve as both a diagnostic and an operational asset, bridging the gap between model transparency and performance across a variety of applications.

B. APPLICATION

In the context of AtmoRep, $A_h \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times N}$ breaks down further to $A_h \in \mathbb{R}^{(n_t \times n_v \times n_\theta \times n_\phi) \times (n_t \times n_v \times n_\theta \times n_\phi)}$. Here, n_t represents the number of time steps with a 3-hour interval, n_v corresponds to five vertical levels approximating pressure levels at 546, 693, 850, and 947 hPa, n_θ and n_ϕ are the longitudinal and latitudinal grid points with a step size of 2.25 degrees each. The attention mechanism operates on localized neighborhoods typically of size $12 \times 5 \times 12 \times 6$ for time, vertical level, longitude, and latitude, although different fields sometimes have different levels of granularity. When working on visually displaying the attention maps for AtmoRep, the images generated were generally 12×6 blocks of longitude and latitude chosen for a specific batch, time, level, and attention head. Given how many options there are for image generation, producing all the attention maps for a given run would be unfeasible, not to mention choices of where to obtain the attention maps from and how to reduce their dimension. Thus, when visually displaying attention maps for such a large model, choices have to be made on what information is most important to display and how to display it.

Fig. 7 displays vorticity data for Hurricane Katrina, accompanied by 16 distinct attention maps, each representing a different head. The AtmoRep network employs multihead attention, wherein we partition tokens across the embedding dimension prior to computing attention. This design enables each head to discern distinct features within the data. Our model makes use of 8 self-attention heads, which capture holistic behavior from

Figure 7: Hurricane Katrina and the associated attention maps from all 16 heads.

throughout the model, and 8 cross-attention heads paired with the encoder to pinpoint fine-grained details- all 16 heads are displayed in Fig. 7. Looking at all 16 heads in this way represents one approach to visualizing the attention maps. We fix the position, time, batch, level, obtain the attention map from the last layer of the decoder in the model, and average over the keys for dimension reduction. Despite these constraints, the model’s behavior reveals intriguing characteristics. For instance, it appears to specifically concentrate on the eye of Hurricane Katrina, showing additional substructures. Furthermore, each attention head offers a unique perspective, with heads 2 and 3 displaying particularly divergent focus points. This variation among attention heads, especially with such a large event, not only underscores the model’s capability for nuanced understanding, but also suggests potential avenues for further research into how multihead attention can be optimized for meteorological analysis.

Fig. 8 shows a large vorticity wave evolving over time, along with the corresponding attention images generated by the last cross-attention head. In this case, the final two images are masked to facilitate prediction. Intriguingly, the attention maps appear to successfully track the position of the wave as it advances into the future. By holding all variables constant except for time, this visualization allows us to observe how the model’s attention mechanism effectively tracks dynamic physical features over time. This suggests that our model is not just capable of identifying static features but is also effective in understanding and predicting temporal phenomena, opening the door for additional research into improving forecasting techniques.

Fig. 9 shows attention maps over one spatial batch in the model which corresponds to a longitudinal strip. In this image, attention has been accumulated across the model’s architecture. This is achieved by matrix-multiplying the attention maps from each successive attention block, post-normalization to a mean of zero and a standard deviation of one. In contrast to previous figures, where dimension reduction was performed by averaging over keys, here we take a different approach. We concentrate the attention with respect to a single query positioned near the center of the strip. This method allows us to investigate how the model’s attention evolves and interacts through its multiple layers, while focusing on a specific geographic feature. It also introduces a form of dimensionality reduction that is more targeted, which can be particularly useful when

Figure 8: Large wave and associated attention maps in time.

Figure 9: Accumulated attention with single token dimension reduction over one batch in space.

probing the model’s focus on specific elements within the data.

Our analysis also extends to a more macroscopic scale, as demonstrated in Figure 10. This figure presents a comprehensive view, showing the Earth’s vorticity across the entire globe alongside its corresponding attention map. This global perspective allows us to better understand how the model’s attention mechanisms function when presented with large-scale patterns and interactions. It’s important to clarify, however, that our model is inherently local in its calculations; attention is not computed across the entire Earth’s surface. Despite this localized focus, examining the model from a broader perspective offers valuable insights. It allows us to observe how localized attention mechanisms behave within the context of larger-scale phenomena, even if the model itself doesn’t perform global attention calculations. This can provide clues into the model’s limitations and potential areas for improvement, particularly when considering applications that require a more global understanding of meteorological phenomena.

These results are presented in an interactive web UI, available at:

<https://www.atmorep.org/attention/attention.html>

In this interface, users have the option to specify various parameters for more focused analysis. Choices include

Figure 10: Full map of the Earth’s vorticity and corresponding attention map below on August 26th, 2005.

selecting the batch to analyze, determining whether to view attention maps across different dimensions such as space, heads, time, or vertical levels, and opting for either accumulated or last-layer attention. Users can also select their preferred method of dimensionality reduction, whether by averaging or focusing on a single token. Additionally, an option to apply a softmax function to the images is available for enhanced visualization. This interactive platform is designed to provide a comprehensive, yet customizable, exploration of the model’s behavior.

Figure 11: Example from attention webUI.

4 LOOKING FORWARD

A. POTENTIAL FOR ATTENTION MAPS

While visually inspecting attention maps can offer intuitive insights into the model's behavior and is valuable for debugging or initial interpretations, this approach has limitations. It can be subjective and may not reveal the full scope of what the attention mechanisms are capturing. However, coupling visual examination with quantitative data analysis on attention metrics can provide a more comprehensive understanding. By quantifying attention values, one can employ statistical methods to rigorously validate what is being observed. This can be particularly useful for identifying patterns or anomalies that may not be immediately obvious through visual inspection alone. Furthermore, data analysis techniques can enable the optimization of attention heads for specific tasks, thereby pushing the boundaries of what the model can accomplish. In sum, while visual interpretations provide a good starting point, a data-driven approach can offer deeper insights and propel the model's capabilities to new heights.

When the attention maps are examined at these larger scales, they hold the promise of being instrumental in a range of applications beyond basic weather forecasting. For example, in the realm of disaster preparedness, these maps could offer invaluable insights, enabling emergency services to allocate resources more effectively by identifying areas at higher risk and doing so faster than the current methods. Additionally, they have the potential to enrich climate science research by illuminating the intricate relationships between various meteorological factors, thereby helping to refine and improve long-term climate models. In renewable energy sectors such as wind and solar, understanding the attention patterns could provide clues to optimize energy output by identifying influential weather patterns. Integration with existing meteorological sensing technology may give rise to weather monitoring systems that are both more adaptive and dynamic. While it's crucial to emphasize that the efficacy of these varied applications remains to be confirmed through rigorous testing, the potential utility of AtmoRep's attention maps in these areas is both expansive and exciting, meriting further in-depth exploration.

B. INTEGRATION WITH INTERTWIN

During my internship at CERN, I worked on an ambitious project to integrate AtmoRep with interTwin, a general-purpose platform designed for AI/ML workflows in digital twins. InterTwin aims to simplify machine learning operations (MLOps), providing an intuitive interface for ML researchers to manage workflows with limited engineering overhead. My role was to adapt AtmoRep's attention-based weather prediction model to this platform, aiming for a seamless interface that could benefit from interTwin's capabilities in model training, evaluation, logging, and hyperparameter tuning.

However, we encountered compatibility issues during the integration process. The existing digital twin model within interTwin was not yet mature enough to accommodate the specialized requirements of AtmoRep. Rather than making sweeping changes to AtmoRep, as initially suggested, we pivoted our focus towards improving the robustness of interTwin. We engaged in intensive discussions and planning sessions to identify the limitations of the existing system and strategize on future upgrades.

Looking forward, we hope to eventually achieve a successful integration between the two platforms. The goal is to leverage interTwin's MLOps capabilities to enhance AtmoRep's performance and make its attention-based models more interpretable and actionable. This would not only broaden the potential use cases for AtmoRep but would also serve as a milestone in creating a more versatile and robust interTwin platform. We believe that with focused efforts and iterative development, this integration will become feasible, opening up new avenues for advanced AI/ML workflows in the realm of digital twins.

5 CONCLUSION

The advent of transformers has had a profound impact far beyond their original domain in Natural Language Processing (NLP). Their unparalleled ability to capture intricate long-range dependencies and hierarchical structures in data has allowed us to expand their use and introduce novel methods in atmospheric modeling. In this context, we presented AtmoRep, an innovative framework that leverages these transformative capabilities for the large-scale representation learning of atmospheric dynamics. AtmoRep has demonstrated impressive performance in a range of downstream applications, thereby reinforcing the robustness and versatility of transformer architectures in the field of atmospheric modeling.

My research has been primarily focused on attention maps in AtmoRep. Extracting and understanding these matrices presented both technical and philosophical challenges. Technical, in obtaining and setting up the matrices for visualization, and philosophical questions in determining how best to organize and prioritize the maps. Attention matrices in transformers are computed at different layers, such as encoders, decoders, or individual attention blocks, and the ideal layer to extract these maps from is an active area of research. Here, we compared last layer vs. accumulated attention to glean a more nuanced understanding of the model's behavior. Once we obtain an attention matrix, its dimensionality must be simplified for visualization. We employed two main strategies to accomplish this, namely averaging across keys and focusing on a single query. In deciding how to display the maps we also employed different strategies from temporal organization to head visualization. The potential applications of attention maps in AtmoRep and transformers at large present promising avenues for exploration. We look forward to witnessing how this technology develops in the future and what applications will be next.

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